

Mitigation of Radar Interference with WiMAX Systems

Lawrence Cohen¹, Erica Daly^{1,2}, Jean DeGraaf¹, and Kim Scheff¹
¹Radar Division, Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC 20375
²University of Illinois, Urbana, IL 61801

Abstract--- In this paper, the effect of radar-induced electromagnetic interference (EMI) on a WiMAX base station receiver is investigated through the use of MATLAB models. The three types of radar pulses investigated include: a short, wideband, chirp pulse; a long, narrowband, chirp pulse; and a long, sinusoidal pulse. The benefits of superimposing these pulses in the guard interval and/or guard band of the WiMAX waveform are explored.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless systems, such as the Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX), occupy spectrum formerly used mostly by radar. WiMAX is originally based on the IEEE 802.16-2004 standard [1], which specifies orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), as the means for encoding data bits onto multiple orthogonal carriers as a way of transmitting groups of symbols. Each of these individual carriers comprises a symbol and provides resistance to multipath due to each carrier's relatively slow symbol rate. Modulation schemes ranging from BPSK through 64 QAM are employed [2]. Figure 1 [3] is a pictorial showing how the OFDM carriers are arranged in time and frequency. What also can be seen are guard intervals (shown in black) in between the rainbow colored data symbols. These guard intervals insulate the OFDM symbols from interfering with each other. Also note that when the subcarriers are superimposed in frequency, they have zero energy at the center frequencies of neighboring subcarriers. It is this property which makes the OFDM subcarriers orthogonal to each other.

For the modeled experiment, an OFDMA format is exploited as it is representative of where WiMAX is evolving in concert with IEEE Standard 802.16m. To gain a better perspective of the simulations discussed in this paper, it is important to gain another viewpoint of how data is transmitted on a WiMAX channel. Figure 2 depicts OFDM in time and frequency. The WiMAX spectrum is allocated to

Figure 1: OFDM pictorial (Courtesy of Agilent)

a number of channels at designated RF carrier frequencies. The data to be transmitted is grouped into packets. These packets are conveyed by one or more subcarriers within a WiMAX channel over the course of one or more OFDM symbol periods. The information contained in each packet can be decoded independently. In order to avoid interfering with information contained in adjacent WiMAX channels, the signal contains buffer zones between adjacent channels called *guard bands*. In Figure 2, information is shown as sparkled gray areas, while the guard intervals and guard bands are shown in blue.

Figure 2: WiMAX Structure

In principle, if the radar signal stays within the guard bands and intervals during a radar transmission, it avoids interfering with the WiMAX signal. Figure 3 shows the structure of a

single OFDM symbol in a single WiMAX channel depicted on a spectrogram. Note that a short radar pulse may fit within the guard interval, and a narrowband radar pulse may fit within the guard band.

Figure 3: Structure of One OFDM Symbol in One Channel

II. SHORT PULSE SIMULATION

The first simulation to be described involves a time domain approach. Figure 4 shows the placement of the radar pulse relative to the WiMAX signal on a spectrogram.

Figure 4: Time domain approach showing the radar signal (in pink) superimposed on the WiMAX signal spectrogram.

TABLE I
TIME DOMAIN APPROACH CHARACTERISTICS

Radar Parameters	WiMAX Parameters
Pulse width: 100 ns	2048 subcarriers
Carrier frequency: 3.4 GHz	24 OFDM symbols
Gaussian pulse shape	200 MHz filter
300 MHz chirp	20 MHz BW

The WiMAX receiver was modeled as a base station. A 20 MHz bandpass filter is applied to the WiMAX receiver front end, as is typical in WiMAX receivers. The radar signal at the WiMAX base station is 40 dB higher in power relative to the WiMAX signal.

Figure 5: Radar pulse not in synchronization with the guard band

First, the effect on WiMAX of a short pulse that is not synchronized with WiMAX's guard interval is investigated. Figure 5 shows the presence of the radar pulse among the information OFDM carriers. Note the guard interval between 210 and 215 ns. The spectrogram in Figure 5 shows the potential for interference by the dark band between 40 to 55 ns across the WiMAX receiver's bandwidth. Figure 6 shows the distortion of the WiMAX constellation due to the radar pulse. The constellation, with no noise, is symmetric, with 64 points (8x8) in a square array. Figure 6, however, shows the constellation smeared and in complete disarray. Demodulating the correct constellation point would be impossible. Shown in Figure 7 is a graph with error vector magnitude (EVM) versus frequency. EVM [4] is defined as the magnitude of the error vector received to that of the ideal vector of a digital modulation format, such as 64 QAM, where the constellation points are a product of the in-phase and quadrature components. Each constellation point has an assigned symbol value. Because of the small decision area in which to detect the correct constellation point or symbol, an EVM of less than 3 percent is considered necessary for reliable demodulation of the constellation points. As seen in Figure 7, this 3 percent margin is not achieved.

Figure 6: WiMAX constellation corrupted by a short pulse

Figure 7: Error vector magnitude (EVM) of the WiMAX constellation corrupted by an unsynchronized radar pulse

Figure 10: EVM of the WiMAX constellation unaffected by a synchronized radar pulse

If the radar pulse is now synchronized with the guard interval, the results are different. Figure 8 shows how the radar pulse is contained within the guard interval between symbols 1 and 2. The radar pulse is still 40 dB above the WiMAX signal, but because the radar interfering signal is contained outside of the symbol area, interference is not introduced into the constellation. Figure 8 shows 64 discernable constellation points along with an EVM versus frequency graph below 3 percent.

Figure 8: Radar pulse synchronized with the guard interval

III. NARROWBAND PULSE SIMULATION

In addition to the time domain approach, a frequency domain approach is explored where the guard band, as shown previously in Figure 3, is exploited. Figure 11 depicts this concept.

The simulated pulse is a 25 μ s long, linear FM chirp with a 2.7 MHz bandwidth. At the WiMAX base station, the radar pulse is 20 dB above the WiMAX signal. Table II summarizes both the radar and WiMAX characteristics.

Figure 11: Frequency domain approach

Figure 9: WiMAX constellation unaffected by a radar pulse that is synchronized with WiMAX's guard interval

TABLE II
FD APPROACH #1 CHARACTERISTICS

Radar Parameters	WiMAX Parameters
Pulse width: 25 μ s	2048 subcarriers
Carrier frequency: 3.4 GHz	24 OFDM symbols
Rectangular pulse shape	1.8 MHz guard bands
2.0 MHz bandpass filter	20 MHz BW

Figure 12 depicts the radar pulse and its relationship to the WiMAX signal. The spectrogram on the bottom shows the radar pulse and marks the WiMAX guard bands. The top guard band includes the high frequency guard band of the channel of interest as well as the low frequency guard band

of the adjacent channel. Similarly, the bottom guard band as shown in Figure 12 spans guard bands from two adjacent channels. The upper left plot shows a cross section in frequency of the radar energy taken along the purple line through the spectrogram. The upper right graph shows the time domain representation of the radar pulse.

First, the effect on a WiMAX system of a long, narrowband radar pulse that is not aligned to the guard band in frequency is investigated. The radar pulse is centered at 3.4 GHz, which places it in the center of the information-bearing region of the WiMAX signal.

Figure 12: Introduction of the radar pulse with respect to the WiMAX transmission.

The slightly canted horizontal line shows the relative power spectral density with respect to time and frequency. Figure 13 shows the constellation points in disarray and the accompany EVM (should be less than 3 percent) which shows the inability of the receiver to discern the correct constellation points.

Figure 13: WiMAX constellation corrupted by a radar pulse that is misaligned in frequency

Figure 14: EVM of the WiMAX constellation corrupted by a radar pulse that is misaligned in frequency

The radar pulse is now placed within the upper guard band of the WiMAX transmission at 3.41 GHz. In order to reduce the side lobes of the radar signal, the pulse is also filtered by a 2 MHz bandpass filter before transmission. Figure 15 shows how the radar pulse is situated in the upper guard band. As can be seen from the spectrogram, most of the radar pulse’s RF energy is contained in the upper guard band shown by the blue dotted line. The radar energy that is outside of the guard band is at least 5 dB below the WiMAX signal. Figures 16 and 17 show the constellation and EVM diagrams for the radar pulse placed within the upper guard band respectively.

Unlike the constellation diagram of Figure 13, the constellation points of Figure 16 are discernable, although noticeable symbol errors are apparent do to the smearing in the constellation. The $\frac{3}{4}$ coding rate convolutional error correction code employed in the model is able to recover all of the information bits transmitted during the simulation. In addition, note that the EVM tends to migrate upward to 10 percent at the higher extent of the band beyond 3.405 GHz.

Figure 15: Radar pulse situated in a guard band

Figure 16: WiMAX constellation only moderately corrupted by a radar pulse that is aligned in frequency to fall within the WiMAX guard band

Figure 17: EVM diagram for radar pulse within a WiMAX guard band

IV. ORTHOGONAL PULSE SIMULATION

Finally, a long, sinusoidal, radar pulse that is orthogonal to the OFDM signal is explored. Figure 18 depicts this concept. Although the radar signal has energy in the information band of the WiMAX signal, it places no energy at the center frequencies of every subcarrier in the WiMAX signal. Therefore, the radar signal does not interfere with the WiMAX decoding operation. Such a signal is beneficial in certain configurations of WiMAX that do not have a wide guard band. It is especially beneficial when the WiMAX spectrum is divided into many narrowband channels, as a radar tone may be inserted in the guard interval of each channel, creating a long, wideband pulse.

Figure 18: Orthogonal Waveform Approach

Since the pulse must preserve its orthogonality with the WiMAX signal, it must adhere to many restrictions. The pulse must begin and end in the guard interval of the WiMAX signal, which means that its length must be approximately an integer multiple of the OFDM symbol period. It also must be very precisely aligned to a frequency in WiMAX's guard band that is orthogonal to its subcarriers.

The simulated pulse is a 209.6 μs long sinusoid that is 20 dB above the WiMAX signal at the WiMAX base station. Table III summarizes both the radar and WiMAX characteristics.

Figure 19 shows how the radar pulse is introduced among the WiMAX subcarriers. The spectrogram on the right shows the radar energy (purple vertical line) in the WiMAX subcarrier region.

TABLE III
ORTHOGONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Radar Parameters	WiMAX Parameters
Pulse width: 209.6 μ s	256 subcarriers
Frequency: 3.400625 GHz	96 OFDM symbols
Rectangular pulse shape	134 kHz guard bands
Sinusoidal pulse	1.25 MHz BW

Figure 19: Radar pulse orthogonal to the WiMAX signal

Figure 20: WiMAX unaffected by an orthogonal radar pulse

Figure 21: EVM of the WiMAX constellation unaffected by an orthogonal radar pulse

Figures 20 and 21 reveal that the orthogonal radar pulse does not degrade the WiMAX system.

V. CONCLUSION

The explosion of wireless systems, such as WiMAX, in the traditional radar bands worldwide has already demonstrated that the two systems are unable to coexist utilizing conventional methods of frequency management and operation. Radars, particularly the high power variants, e.g. megawatts of peak power, operated either on-shore or offshore in a littoral environment promise to wreak havoc on a WiMAX system’s ability to detect the proper constellation point particularly when a dense constellation, such as 64 QAM, is involved. It is possible, however, to transmit a radar pulse within the WiMAX spectrum that does not degrade the performance of the WiMAX system. Further work will involve developing methodologies for measuring the guard intervals and bands in real time and adapting a radar system to transmit within these intervals and bands.

V. REFERENCES

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